

PREDICTION OF ANISOTROPIC THERMAL EXPANSION BEHAVIOR OF FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES AT CRYOGENIC TEMPERATURE

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1 Introduction

Owing to the structural performance by superior specific stiffness, fiber reinforced polymeric (FRP) composites have been increasingly adopted in many industrial fields. Also, FRP composites have been paid attention as the candidate materials for low temperature storage tanks in the aerospace and LNG transport applications [1].

However, thermal stress mismatch between fibers and polymer matrix may give rise to the degradation of composites in the cryogenic circumstance. Therefore thermal properties of composite materials should be well characterized at the low temperature environment in order to reduce the structural damage and precise numerical techniques are required for the structural design. Furthermore the accurate measurement and prediction techniques for the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) are required for the FRP composites at low temperature.

Conventional measurement method for CTE is to use dilatometer, interferometry or laser instrument. However these are not adequate for the low temperature environment and very complex to use [2,3]. Here, CTE was measured by utilizing the strain gage, which can guarantee the accuracy at the low temperature [4].

For the prediction of CTE, there have been several methods such as a simple rule of mixture, a homogenization of cell modeling [5] and FE analysis using representative volume element [6]. However, the accuracy is insufficient since many methods use temperature-independent properties based on material supplier's data. Also, most prediction works were for UD composites [7,8] and it is difficult to find out-of-plane analysis for the plain woven composites [9] especially at the low temperature.

In this work, CTE of the carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) composite was measured at cryogenic temperature utilizing G-M type

cryocooler and strain gauge. Two directional properties were considered along the in-plane and through-the-thickness directions in order to investigate anisotropic thermal expansion behavior of CFRP composites.

Also, two simple and accurate prediction methods were suggested for CTE of CFRP composite system considering temperature-dependent elastic behaviors and CTEs of fibers and polymer matrix. One is the analytic equation and the other is finite element (FE) analysis based calculation. Through the inverse FE calculation for the unit cell of the composite, the CTE of the carbon fiber is determined to follow the thermal behavior of the CFRP composite. Considering different matrix based CFRP composites, the prediction capability was examined by utilizing the inversely determined CTE of the carbon fiber. Through the prediction, the anisotropic thermal expansion behavior was examined by comparing with experimental results.

2 Experiment

2.1 Materials

The carbon fabric was a plain weave (TR-30S; Mitshubishi) and epoxy resin (YD-128; Kukdo Chemicals) was considered for the CFRP composite. The curing agent was KBH-1089 (Kukdo Chemicals) and mixed at 0.9 weight fraction to the epoxy resin. The CFRP composite was manufactured by the vacuum assisted resin transfer molding process. To measure both in-plane and through-the-thickness CTEs, 250 carbon fabrics were laminated and were cut having 5.0 mm thickness.

2.2 Measurement of CTE using Strain Gage at Cryogenic Temperature

Here, the cryogenic environment was established using a G-M type cryocooler (SRDK-205D series; SHI) and a cryogenic temperature controller (Lakeshore 331S). The temperature was monitored by Lakeshore 218 series and the silicon diode type DT-670 temperature sensors were used.

Also the sample holder was manufactured using the oxygen free cooper plate. Since the copper plate is a highly thermal conductive material, the temperature of specimen can be easily cooled down to the cryogenic temperature. Also, the cryogenic system was vacuum-insulated as 10^{-7} Torr and aluminum-shielded to minimize thermal radiation loss due to the huge difference between inside's low temperature and outside's room temperature.

To measure the CTE, two quarter-bridge type strain gage circuits are considered for the measuring sample and the reference specimen (titanium silicate) [10] using cryogenic strain gage (CFLA-6-350-11 series; TML). Since the titanium silicate has very low CTE at the cryogenic temperature ($-1 \sim 0 \mu\epsilon$), it is commonly used as the reference material for measuring CTE. The thermal output (ε_{TO}) is a function of CTEs of both sample (α_S) and strain gage (α_G) as well as a thermal coefficient of resistivity of strain gage (β_G) as described in Eq. 1.

$$\varepsilon_{TO} = \left[\beta_G / F_G + (\alpha_S - \alpha_G) \right] \Delta T \quad (1)$$

where F_G is a gauge factor and ΔT is temperature change. Considering the thermal output difference between the sample and the reference specimen (R), CTE of the sample becomes

$$\alpha_S = \alpha_R + \left(\varepsilon_{TO(S)} - \varepsilon_{TO(R)} \right) / \Delta T \quad (2)$$

since α_R is known [11]. Here, thermal outputs were measured from room temperature (RT) to 15K.

3 Prediction

3.1 Analytic method

Based on the classical rule of mixture, the thermal strain of composite becomes

$$\varepsilon_C^T = \left(c_f E_f v_f \varepsilon_f^T + E_m v_m \varepsilon_m^T \right) / E_C \quad (3)$$

where subscripts f, m and C represent fiber, matrix and composite. Considering temperature dependency in Eq. (3), CTE of composite becomes

$$\alpha_C = \frac{1}{E_C^2} \left[E_C Q(T) - \frac{dE_C}{dT} P(T) \right] \quad (4)$$

Fig. 1. Unit cell structure for FE calculation

Fig. 2. CTE of CF/epoxy and CF/CTBN composite

where

$$P(T) = c_f E_f v_f \int \alpha_f dT + E_m v_m \int \alpha_m dT$$

$$Q(T) = c_f v_f \left(\frac{dE_f}{dT} \int \alpha_f dT + E_f \alpha_f \right) \quad (5)$$

$$+ v_m \left(\frac{dE_m}{dT} \int \alpha_m dT + E_m \alpha_m \right)$$

3.2 Inverse FE analysis

Considering the unit cell as shown in Fig. 1, numerical FE simulation was performed for the thermal compaction. In order to find the CTE of carbon fiber, inverse calculation was carried out to fit minimize the difference between experimental results and calculation data using the Newton-Raphson method. Here the commercial FE software, ABAQUS/Standard was utilized.

4 Results

4.1 Validation of Inverse FE based analysis

Fig. 2 shows CTE of carbon fiber calculated from the inverse FE analysis for the CF/epoxy composite. As shown in Fig. 2, the inverse method correctly follows the experimental data. Also the result by the analytic model and constant CTE based FE analysis gave good agreement with experimental result. However, the tendency is slightly different. As expected, the simple rule of mixture showed large

deviation due to ignoring of temperature-dependent behaviors.

In order to verify the developed CTE prediction methods, the same FE simulations were performed for the carbon fiber/CTBN-epoxy composite. The numerical results were compared with experimental results as shown in Fig. 2. In this case, the inverse FE analysis showed better agreement than the analytic model. Even though the order of values are almost similar each other, the tendencies were opposite. Since the crimping geometry is ignored in the analytic model, such discrepancy occurs at the different composite system.

4.2 Anisotropic CTE behavior

The anisotropic thermal expansion behaviors of CFRP composites and epoxy resin were shown in Fig. 3. As for the in-plane direction of CFRP composite, CTE was the least and didn't show a significant change with temperature decrease, since the in-plane thermal expansion behavior is dominantly dependent on the reinforced carbon fiber. The through-the-thickness CTE of CFRP composite and the CTE of epoxy resin showed higher values than the in-plane CTE of CFRP and decreasing behaviors as temperature drop. Therefore, the through-the-thickness thermal behavior of the composite is mostly dependent on the epoxy resin owing to the relatively large amount of resin along the thickness direction in the laminated composite. Especially for the room temperature results, the CTE values were measured as $4.4 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $40.4 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ for the in-plane direction of the composite and epoxy resin, which were almost similar results to the previous work [12].

Note that the through-the-thickness CTE of CFRP composite doesn't follow the rule of mixture for the polymeric composite since it was observed larger than the CTE of pure epoxy resin. Therefore it can be seen that such large CTE in the through-the-thickness direction is due to the kinematic constraints of the laminated CFRP composite structure.

To examine this phenomenon, following simple analysis has been carried out. Considering a neighboring unit cell structure of a plain woven composite, the matrix dominant region can be assumed to be surrounded by fiber yarns as shown in Fig. 4. Assuming that the contact area of the matrix

Fig. 3. Experimental results for anisotropic CTEs of CFRP composite and epoxy resin

Fig. 4. Modeling for anisotropic CTE prediction

with fibers is confined, in-plane thermal expansion behavior of the laminated matrix is limited by the in-plane fiber. From the volume conservation of the matrix,

$$\frac{1}{V_m} \frac{dV_m}{dT} = \frac{2}{L_m} \frac{dL_m}{dT} + \frac{1}{H_m} \frac{dH_m}{dT} \quad (7)$$

where V_m is a volume, L_m is a length and H_m is a height of a representative matrix, respectively. Here, L_m is confined by the in-plane thermal expansion behavior of fibers. Therefore, Eq. (7) becomes

$$\alpha_m^T = 3\alpha_m - 2\bar{\alpha}_f^L \quad (8)$$

where

$$3\alpha_m = \frac{1}{V_m} \frac{dV_m}{dT}, \alpha_m^T = \frac{1}{H_m} \frac{dH_m}{dT}, \bar{\alpha}_f^L = \frac{1}{L_m} \frac{dL_m}{dT} \quad (9)$$

Also, considering kinematic parameters a and b from the unit cell structure as shown in Fig. 4 with fiber's directional CTEs from the unit,

$$\bar{\alpha}_f^L = \frac{a+2b}{2a+2b} \alpha_f^L + \frac{a}{2a+2b} \alpha_f^T \quad (10)$$

As shown in Fig. 5, the calculated results agreed well with the experimental results and also showed

Fig. 5. Calculated and measured CTEs

the largest CTE values in the through-the-thickness direction of composite.

When applying only the rule of mixture without considering the kinematic consideration, the obtained CTE values were 18.6 and 24.2 $\mu\epsilon/^\circ\text{C}$ for the in-plane and through-the-thickness directions. This means that the rule of mixture cannot explain the larger behavior in the through-the-thickness direction. Therefore, such a large anisotropic thermal expansion behavior along the through-the-thickness direction of CFRP composite is originated from the kinematic constraints by the surrounding plain-weave fibers.

5 Conclusions

In this work, an analytic model and FE analysis based method were suggested to predict CTE of carbon fiber composite at low temperature. Through the inverse numerical calculation, CTE of carbon fiber was estimated to exactly follow the thermal contraction behavior of plain weave composites. Utilizing this, the thermal behavior was calculated for the different matrix system such as a carbon fiber/CTBN epoxy composite and results showed that the FE analysis method gave better agreement than the analytical model with experimental results. Also, the in-plane and through-the-thickness thermal expansion behaviors of CFRP composite were measured at the cryogenic temperature using the G-M type cryocooler system. The experimental results showed that the in-plane thermal expansion behavior was almost unchanging due to the carbon fiber dominant dependency. The through-the-thickness CTE was decreased as temperature drop owing to the matrix dominant laminated structure. Also, it was observed larger than the CTE of pure epoxy and

this anisotropic behavior was successfully explained by a simple analytical approach considering the kinematic constraints of the interlaminar matrix in the unit cell structure.

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